

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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EFFECTIVE METHODS AND FORMS OF UPBRINGING IN INSTILLING IN STUDENTS THE VALUES OF NATIONAL DECENCY.

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Annotation. This article analyzes the effective methods and forms of upbringing used to instill in students the values of national decency. On the basis of modern approaches, the importance of effective methods and forms in spiritual and educational work is highlighted.

Keywords: Upbringing, method, morality, behavior, society, spirituality, or non-identity.

Introduction:

National ethical and moral norms represent the spiritual heritage of every nation and play a vital role in the upbringing of the younger generation. Through various methods and forms of education, these values are instilled into the consciousness of youth. Educational methods serve to shape moral standards within the pedagogical process. All aspects of morality develop in an interconnected manner, contributing to the progress of society and the perfection of humanity. Morality begins to form from the earliest stages of human life and serves as an internal spiritual factor that lays the foundation for personal development. A person, through education and upbringing, acquires specific norms of etiquette and morality, gains knowledge, develops skills through labor and experience, masters a profession, and attains qualifications. This allows an individual to fully express their abilities and talents in one or more fields. On the foundation of morality arise concepts such as conscience, duty, faith, dignity, honor, and sincerity. Similarly, the concept of **etiquette** is closely related to morality and plays a significant role in the upbringing of children.

The term *etiquette* (from the Arabic word *adab*, meaning "manners") refers to the socially accepted norms of behavior and represents the external aspect of a person's spiritual life, which becomes evident in their interactions with others. Etiquette encompasses moral principles, standards, the level of one's upbringing, and aesthetic

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ideals. It includes rules related to how a person should behave in public, how they communicate with others, how they organize their personal life and leisure time, and how they present themselves outwardly. For example, it covers values such as honor, modesty, chastity, humility, and politeness.

Rules of morality and etiquette should be taught not only at home by parents, but also at school by teachers and within the local community by neighbors. In the process of this teaching, it is essential to use various methods and forms of educational approaches.

MainPart:

A child naturally desires to participate actively in the life of society. Therefore, an educator must understand how, under what conditions, and in what kind of relationship to guide and nurture the child. To do so, teachers and caregivers need to be familiar with specific methods and know how to apply them correctly.

When does a student open their heart to a teacher? It happens when the teacher is a friend, when they can understand the student in any situation, and when they can provide proper guidance. A teacher who wishes to educate a student must first earn their affection and trust. Only when a student genuinely likes the teacher will they truly listen; and if they are listening, they are also understanding.

To explain and guide effectively, the teacher needs a method. The word "*method*" originates from Greek and means "a way" or "a path." Folk pedagogy, particularly in the Uzbek tradition, reflects the rich and nuanced approaches to morality, etiquette, and upbringing, encompassing all aspects of ethical development.

Educational methods are pedagogical tools aimed at shaping students' moral qualities and fostering ethical behavior.

Among these methods are:

1. **Explanation** (storytelling, teaching)
2. **Habituation through practice** (creating habits, training through repetition)
3. **Setting an example** (giving advice, apologizing, speaking about good deeds, being a role model)
4. **Admonition and moral guidance** (encouragement, persuasion, making requests, pleading, expressing wishes and desires, approval, expressing gratitude, offering prayers and blessings, wishing success, etc.)

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5. **Reproach and punishment** (emphasis, reproach, complaint, reprimand, coercion, scolding, blaming, shaming, intimidation, instilling fear or disgust, making oaths, arguing, physical punishment, and didactic stories)

If we pay attention, the five methods mentioned above represent a unified and holistic approach. Initially, when children do not yet understand the essence of a general process, the educator utilizes the method of setting an example—this emphasizes the importance of students' independent observation. If, even after this, the child fails to grasp the concept, the process or phenomenon is explained through the moral guidance and advice of adults.

However, if the expected outcome is still not achieved, or if the children are unwilling to understand the essence that requires their attention, then—as a last resort—the methods of reproach and punishment may be used. Yet this should always remain the final measure.

According to modern pedagogical principles, reproach and punishment have been proven to be the least effective methods, yielding minimal positive outcomes.

Methods such as instruction, encouragement, setting an example, motivation, punishment, and conversation are applied through different forms of education, including group-based, individual, mass, game-based, and competitive formats. In addition, the use of folklore, literary works, and theatrical elements can significantly enhance the effectiveness of moral and ethical education.

Moral and ethical values are instilled in the minds of young people through spiritual and educational activities. The following methods play a significant role in shaping students' social consciousness: conversation, storytelling, setting an example, self-education, self-analysis, self-assessment, explanation, discussion, practice and instruction, habit formation, assignments, and pedagogical requirements. Among these, conversation holds a particularly important place.

1. **Thematic topics** – including discussions on socio-moral norms, dominant social relationships in society, behavioral rules within a community, and others;
2. **Aesthetic topics** – such as the beauty of nature, interpersonal relationships, and human aesthetics;
3. **Political topics** – including the country's internal and foreign policy, global events, international relations, and similar issues;

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4. **Educational and cognitive topics** – involving subjects like the universe, the world of animals and plants, electronics, and more.

Conversations may also be organized on topics such as socially useful labor, legal awareness, environmental protection, economic literacy, and hygiene. These discussions contribute positively to the overall moral and intellectual development of students.

Conclusion:

The use of effective educational methods and forms in instilling national moral and ethical values is an integral part of modern education. Through these means, young people gain a deep understanding of national values and learn to embody them in their lives.

Teachers must continuously improve their methodological skills and integrate modern technologies into the educational process. National norms of morality and etiquette are social phenomena closely linked to a nation's historical development, culture, traditions, and spiritual values. Effectively instilling these values in the younger generation is considered one of the key tasks of the educational system.

The moral and ethical standards inherent in the Uzbek people—such as respect for elders, care for the young, sincerity, a sense of honor and dignity, honesty, and a strong sense of duty and responsibility—must be deeply embedded in children's consciousness from an early age.

The methods and forms used in the pedagogical process play a crucial role in shaping and consistently reinforcing national moral norms. These include oral instruction (conversations, explanations, advice), practical activities (role-playing, dramatizations), reflective discussions, interactive methods (such as clustering, brainstorming, and debates), as well as the use of information and communication technologies—all of which can significantly enhance the effectiveness of moral education.

Moreover, creating a unified educational environment within the family, school, community, and society at large is a decisive factor in effectively instilling national moral values. In particular, the personal example set by parents and teachers, along with consistency, continuity, and systematic organization in the educational process, plays a vital role in achieving this goal.

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